

HellasQCI

Deploying advanced national QCI systems and networks in Greece

Deliverable D5.1

Report on design of HellasQCI training methodology

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Status – Version: Final
Date: January 19th, 2024
Dissemination Level: Public

Abstract: The deliverable presents the training methodology followed within HellasQCI for providing a training environment for QKD technologies devoted to young researchers, students, academic personnel, IT experts and end users of HellasQCI infrastructure. It also showcases the outcomes and materials derived from the first two HellasQCI workshops, conducted during M09 of the project at the facilities of NTUA and NKUA. These workshops were tailored for the QKD research community and cybersecurity experts, aiming to optimize the content for these specific audiences. Furthermore, the document elaborates on the online platform where all training materials have been uploaded, offering comprehensive insights into the content and diverse features available. Additionally, an appendix containing the comprehensive report of the inaugural training event is provided at the conclusion of the deliverable.

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Document Revision History

Date	Issue	Author/Editor/Contributor	Summary of main changes
30/10/2023	0.1	K. Vyrsokinos	Table of contents and Initial Draft
27/12/2023	0.2	All	First round of edits in the received contributions
5/1/2024	0.3	All	Review and creation of a clean version for final review
9/1/2024	0.4	All	Final Review
11/1/2024	0.5	All	Almost Final version for submission
19/1/2024	0.6	All	Final version for submission

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List of Acronyms

QCI	Quantum Communication Infrastructure
IT	Information Technologies
QKD	Quantum Key Distribution
NKUA	National Kapodistrian University of Athens
NTUA	National Technical University of Athens
FORTH	Foundation for Research and Technology - Hellas
WP	Work Package
EuroQCI	European Quantum Communication infrastructure
PETRUS	EuroQCI coordination and support action
FSO	Free-Space Optical
OGS	Optical Ground Station
RSA	Rivest-Shamir-Adleman
DH	Diffie–Hellman
AES	Advanced Encryption Standard
OTP	One Time Pad
PQC	Post Quantum Cryptography
NIST	National Institute of Standards and Technology
SPAD	Single Photon Avalanche Detectors
QRNG	Quantum Random Number Generators
DV-QKD	Discrete Variable – Quantum Key Distribution
CW	Continuous Wavelength
VOA	Variable Optical Attenuator
PBS	Polarization Beam Splitter
PC	Polarization Controller
WDM	Wavelength Division Multiplexing
SpRS	Spontaneous Raman Scattering
QBER	Quantum Bit Error Rate
ESA	European Space Agency
SKR	Secret Key Rate
NRZ	Non-Return-to-Zero
LDAP	Lightweight directory access protocol
LMS	Learning Management System

Executive Summary

The deliverable reports on the training methodology defined within the HellasQCI project that is aiming to provide a training environment for technical, research and end-users' staff. This report introduces tailored training paths for each of these distinct communities, shedding light on the methodologies applied to cater to their unique needs.

Within the framework of the HellasQCI training plan, two noteworthy workshops were successfully conducted during the third week of September 2023 at the facilities of the National Technical University of Athens (NTUA) and the National and Kapodistrian University of Athens (NKUA). These workshops specifically targeted the research and academic communities, as well as IT security experts, containing both theory and hands on training in QKD basic principles.

Furthermore, the document elaborates on the online platform established to host all training materials, providing a comprehensive overview of its content and various features. This platform serves as a centralized hub for accessing training resources, ensuring easy navigation and engagement for participants from different backgrounds. The deliverable concludes with an informative appendix containing a comprehensive report on the first HellasQCI training events.

1. Introduction

This deliverable provides details about the training methodology considered within HellasQCI project, including the targeted groups for creating an ecosystem of young researchers, security experts and startups or other industrial entities supporting the HellasQCI infrastructure. This national quantum ecosystem will be capable to perform actions like service, maintenance, operation of the QKD devices, development of the new devices and upgrade and update of the existing devices as well as their replacement if needed.

The first outcome of the HellasQCI training plan was the successful organization of the first training event under WP5 of the project featuring two workshops designed for the research and academic communities, as well as IT security experts. The 1st HellasQCI training event was held on September 2023 and it was conducted at NTUA and NKUA facilities where the relevant equipment to QKD basic principles and network is located allowing the hands-on training of the attendees. This deliverable provides a comprehensive overview of the programs of these two workshops, accompanied by a brief analysis of the various talks providing the basic theory followed by the relevant hands-on training activities.

Moreover, the deliverable outlines an online platform intended to serve as a centralized repository for all training materials generated within HellasQCI. This platform is designed to be a single location where trainees can access and retrieve all available resources related to their areas of interest. Throughout the project's duration, each training event organized by HellasQCI will utilize this platform as a repository for all training materials and is intended to be live even after the end of the project. Finally, as an appendix the document is providing the comprehensive report of the first HellasQCI training event with key metrics such as number of attended both physical and online via the GRNET Diavlos livestream service.

1.1 Deliverable Structure

This deliverable is structured as following:

- Section 2 provides an introduction about the training methodology pursued within HellasQCI project.
- Section 3 provides details about the 1st workshop, targeting the Research and Education communities.
- Section 4 follows with the description and content for the Cybersecurity Experts.
- Section 5 offers an overview and comprehensive details covering various aspects of the online platform where all HellasQCI training material is uploaded.
- Section 6 provides the link and a screenshot from the HellasQCI first training event published to the www.tomanifesto.gr website.
- Appendix with the report from the training event.

2. HellasQCI Training Methodology

In line with the strategic goals of EuroQCI in support of the European digital workforce, HellasQCI aims to setup training programs on quantum technologies for the design, deployment and use of next generation highly secure communication and data networks. The aim of the HellasQCI is to train a large number of users in quantum communication technologies, so Greece gets ready for the design, the interfacing and the deployment of next generation highly secure quantum communication networks. As shown in **Figure 1**, there will be programs for (i) academic/research staff, (ii) experts in digital security and (iii) end users and public authorities. The training board, consisting mainly of the academic partners involved in HellasQCI, will elaborate from the start of the project the specific training plan for each group and will mobilise the educational resources to support its implementation. The programs will run in three different stages with different training goals and will be pursued for each category defined in **Figure 1**. Depending on the training needs of each category, different paths have been designed to fit well with the specific needs of each group, and their implementation will be geographically distributed in Athens, Thessaloniki and Heraklion.

Figure 1: High-level description of HellasQCI training plan and indicative training methodologies for each group

In parallel with the initial training plan elaborated within the project, HellasQCI will leverage the training campaigns organised by other EuroQCI initiatives, as well as its participation to the EuroQCI coordination and support action (PETRUS project), where education and training is an essential pillar. More specifically, HellasQCI project will leverage the ongoing work for defining the landscape on the existing education and training programs for quantum technologies in Europe and in the rest of the World. Exploiting the quantum training landscape in Europe and worldwide, HellasQCI will focus on the training programs running in the academic/research institutes and it will attempt to adopt the best training practices and adapt its training methodology based on training methodologies fitting nicely in the training path.

Moreover, HellasQCI will target its active participation in training programs organised from other national initiatives, to directly transfer the best practices and adopt new training methods in the planned workshops.

In support of the training campaigns for the research and academic community, HellasQCI will leverage the training events organised by universities and research centres participating in Quantum Flagship initiative. The Quantum Communication School organised in Padova in May 2024 is an indicative example of training initiatives which can provide significant feedback for assessing the HellasQCI training methodology.

During the first year of HellasQCI, two workshops were organised, focusing on the academic and research communities as well on the experts working on the IT security sector. Comprehensive details as well the highlights of these training events are included in the next paragraphs.

In the HellasQCI proposal the following KPIs were submitted relevant to training activities:

Table 1:KPIs of training activities

KPI	KPI title	Relevant call objective	Relevant WP	KPI threshold	successful	Achieved after 1 st training event
KPI3.1	Total number of training workshop events	O4	WP5	5		2
KPI3.2	Number of short HellasQCI online training tutorials in universities	O4	WP5	3		4
KPI3.3	Number of 1-week summer schools devoted for MSc/PhD students	O4	WP5	1		-
KPI3.4	Total number of participants in the HellasQCI trainings	O4	WP5	160		175 physical presence & 100 online per day
KPI3.5	Online training platform registered users	O4	WP5	60		Platform launched in Jan 2024
KPI3.6	Total number of PhD students participating in HellasQCI activities/ experiments	O4	WP5	7		3
KPI3.7	Integration of HellasQCI training material in MSc and undergraduate courses	O4	WP5	2 MSc courses & 3 Undergraduate programs		1 Undergraduate
KPI3.8	Number of training laboratory events via emulation platforms	O4	WP5	4 (~5-7 participants per event)		2 (>15 participants per event)

Table 1 provides some metrics where each KPI is relatively to the promised values at the start of the project. Three workshops are pending with the two of them focusing again in the research community and the cybersecurity experts. The fifth and last workshop will be devoted to the real end users from the various public and industrial users that are expected to use the HellasQCI infrastructure when completed. In addition, the project plans to organize a Summer School in quantum technologies to raise the awareness of EU students about HellasQCI. It should be emphasized that given the publicity generated from the first two workshops, a significant increase in the number of participants is anticipated for the remaining training event.

It is noteworthy also after the first year of the project KPI3.4 and 3.5 have already been achieved. Furthermore, KPI3.8 has been attained in terms of the number of trainees participating in the laboratory courses.

The initial training methodology included in the HellasQCI project is briefly introduced below:

2.1 Academia and Research institutions

For the academic and research training groups, the initial stage will focus on the preparation of course materials for MSc/PhD programs, which will be combined with workshops and tutorials devoted for postgraduate students. Moreover, the PhD/MSc students in topics relevant to both classical communications and quantum technologies will have the opportunity to participate in dedicated training workshops and tutorials elaborated by the HellasQCI training board. The second stage for this training group will attempt to transfer the acquired expertise during the first stage to practical hands-on experience with actual QKD systems, QKD prototypes and key components operating in the laboratory. Lab-scale training activities, emphasising on the generation manipulation and detection of single-photons, and laboratory demonstrators focusing on QKD transmission systems and performance metrics in deployed QKD systems, will also be part of a carefully designed laboratory training plan. In this way, the students/researchers will acquire a strong theoretical/practical expertise before accessing the demonstration activities in educational/governmental/industrial testbeds deployed in HellasQCI in the last phase of the project. The laboratory exercises will be designed for the needs of the PhD networks, and they will be also available for integration as parts of undergraduate and MSc programs. Different versions of training materials will be prepared in the context of HellasQCI, inspired by the recent trends and roadmaps in building quantum engineering undergraduate programs. Towards the design of the training methodology of HellasQCI, the training plan will also carefully address the different educational needs and academic profiles (e.g., Physics departments, Department of Informatics and Electrical Engineering schools). For this goal, new teaching concepts and novel materials for presenting the principles of quantum optics will be considered.

Aside from the principles of QKD systems and their use in fibre-based transmission systems, earth-to-satellite QKD links will be part of this training program. The principles of Quantum Free-Space Optical (FSO) communications will be initially presented by the academic partners, and the partners involved in the operation of HellasQCI OGSs will provide a tutorial session that will focus on the optical technology, the principles for operating telescopes as OGS, as well as their integration with the terrestrial QKD network.

2.2 Security and IT experts

The training program for security and IT experts will initially cover the principles of cryptography, including state-of-the-art asymmetric (e.g., RSA, DH) and symmetric (e.g., AES, OTP) cryptosystems. Emphasis will be given on their security against both classical and quantum adversaries. An essential part of this program will focus on the fundamental principles underlying the most widely used QKD protocols, providing an overview of their implementation, the threat model, and the conditions under which the QKD promises to deliver quantum safe encryption. Moreover, emphasis will be placed on the integration of QKD solutions into existing cryptographic infrastructure, and there will be hands-on training for the security and IT experts. These will include cryptography related demos and labs as well as practical examples on how to integrate QKD with existing symmetric cryptographic schemes and protocols utilizing algorithms like AES and OTP.

QKD is only a symmetric-key distribution scheme and cannot replicate all the functionalities of public-key cryptography. It is thus likely to be combined with PQC to jointly form the basis for quantum-safe communications. In this context, the training board of HellasQCI will closely monitor the updates in NIST Crypto standards for the PQC and its synergies with the deployed QKD systems, incorporating these updates as part of training materials.

2.3 End users & public authorities

The tutorial session of this training pillar will initially focus primarily on giving a high-level overview of quantum communication for readers not familiar with quantum physics or information theory and will mainly focus on the principles of quantum cryptography allowing for secure data transmission of highly sensitive information. Aside from the introduction to QKD technology, the main part of this tutorial session will address the high-level description of the infrastructure layout devoted for the targeted applications and use cases in governmental and industrial testbeds of HellasQCI. The second part of this training session will put emphasis on the user-interfaces of the deployed infrastructure. To overcome any government security classification policy that may apply to HellasQCI use cases and demos, the experimentation of this training group with the integration approach of QKD resources will be based on a non-operational platform developed to emulate the real environment. In this way, the users will have the opportunity to access the security structure of their organisation and to exploit the available quantum key resources provided by HellasQCI in practical use cases and scenarios for their organisations.

The groups working on the operation of OGSs involved in the HellasQCI will participate in a dedicated training session to get familiar with the principles of Quantum FSO systems, as well with the detection of single photons at the telescopes. The goal of this training activity is to transfer the expertise of groups working on the terrestrial QKD systems to groups operating the telescopes under different conditions and photon noise environments.

3. Workshop for Research and Education communities

The 1st HellasQCI workshop for Research and Education communities was held at the premises of NTUA on 18th and 19th of September 2023 at the National Technical University of Athens, Greece. The training was designed to provide participants with theoretical and practical knowledge on quantum communication, with the goal of enhancing the security of sensitive data and critical infrastructures in Greece and co-creating EuroQCI.

The 4-day event was launched by the new Secretary General of Telecommunications and Post, Konstantinos Karantzalos, followed by welcoming remarks from Prof. Stefanos Kollias, Chairman of the Board of Directors GRNET S.A. The keynote speech, “Quantum Technologies – QKD Landscape in Europe,” was given by Dr. Eleni Diamanti, CNRS research director at Sorbonne University in Paris.

The training was open to cybersecurity professionals, IT managers and engineers, security and IT experts, researchers, students, and practitioners in the field of quantum communication, as well as decision-makers interested in future-proofing their organization’s security infrastructure. Participants could attend in person or via livestream through the GRNET DIAVLOS service. The event had two different thematic axes, namely the “Workshop on Quantum Key Distribution (QKD) Systems” held on 18 and 19 of September and the “Workshop on Cybersecurity with QKD Systems and Post-Quantum Cryptography (PQC)” held on 21 and 22 of September. The two workshops were well-received, with an average of 100 attendees at the first workshop and 75 at the second. In total, 175 unique people attended the workshops. Additionally, an average of 100 people per day participated online via the GRNET Diavlos livestream service. Sixteen trainers provided insights and knowledge on quantum communication.

The schedule of the workshop is listed in the following table.

Table 2: 1st Day Training - September 18th, 2023

Welcoming Session Moderator: Yannis Rizopoulos, Journalist (Boussias Media) Location: NTUA Zografou Campus Multimedia Amphitheatre	
09:00 – 09:10	Welcoming Remarks by Prof. Konstantinos Karantzalos, Secretary General of Telecommunications & Posts, Hellenic Ministry of Digital Governance
09:10 – 09:20	Welcoming Remarks by Prof. Stefanos Kollias, Chairman of the Board of Directors GRNET S.A.
09:25 – 09:40	Keynote speech “Quantum Technologies - QKD Landscape in Europe” by Dr. Eleni Diamanti, CNRS research director at Sorbonne University in Paris
09:40 – 09:50	“HellasQCI project overview and synergies with EuroQCI”

	by Dr. Ilias Papastamatiou, HellasQCI Project Coordinator, GRNET S.A.
09:50 – 09:55	“Overview of Four Day HellasQCI Training” by Prof. Konstantinos Vyrsoinos, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki - AUTH
09:55 – 10:10	Q&A
10:10 – 10:25	Coffee Break
Second Session: Moderator: Giannis Gianoulis, ICCS/GRNET Location: NTUA Zografou Campus Multimedia Amphitheatre	
10:25 – 11:00	Eleni Diamanti, CNRS CNRS research director at Sorbonne University in Paris Plenary Session
11:00 – 11:30	George Nikolopoulos, FORTH Basic Principles of QKD
11:30 – 12:15	Konstantinos Vyrsoinos, AUTH QRNGs
12:15 – 13:00	George Kanellos, NKUA QKD Networks
13:00 – 14:00	Lunch Break
14:00 – 14:45	Giannis Giannoulis, NTUA/GRNET From billion photons to single photon experimental setups
14:45 – 15:05	Ilias Balampanis, Space Hellas SA QKD with Raspberry PI’s as encryptors/decryptors
15:05 – 15:30	Homer Papadopoulos, NCSR QKD with PQC for a Healthcare use case
15:30 – 15:45	Deirdre Kilbane, WIT IrelandQCI
15:45 – 16:00	Konstantinos Katzis, EUC CyQCI

16:00 – 16:15	Piotr Rydlichowski, PSNC PIONIER- Q
16:15-16:45	Conclusions and Discussion (Q&A)

The content of the **Lectures** is provided in the following list:

- **“Basic Principles of QKD”** by Georgios M. Nikolopoulos

The talk aimed at a non-specialized audience and gives an introduction to Quantum Key Distribution (QKD). After a brief introduction to the so-called key-distribution problem, the presentation focuses on the main physical principles underlying the operation and the security of QKD protocols, including the no-cloning theorem, the measurement of quantum states, and the behavior of single-photon states. Subsequently, the presentation revolves around the main stages, as well as possible attacks against ideal QKD protocols. The last part of the talk discusses practical issues, which occur when one tries to implement a QKD protocol.

- **“QRNGs”** by Konstantinos Vyrsokinos

This talk was oriented to the presentation of Quantum Random Number Generators that is one of the main components of QKD equipment. The short course started with the general description of Random Number Generators, their classification in pseudo- and true random generators, with the latter ones leading to quantum random number generators. Then a list of optical quantum random generators is presented providing also the physical system of the various entropy sources and the list of performance metrics. Finally, there is a short description of an integrated InP QRNG circuit evaluated by AUTH with subsequent presentation of NIST statistical testing.

- **“QKD Networks”** by George Kanellos

The presentation focused on outlining the key technologies for implementing large scale QKD networks deployed in the field along with classical telecom equipment as well as providing a brief reference to the key principles of the quantum internet, as a term that refers to general purpose quantum communications networks. In particular, the presentation was divided in three sections:

Section 1: QKD Networks initiated the discussion by analyzing the limitations of QKD technology, then focused on providing the generic concept of Quantum key management concept presenting the current standards and approaches in the networks development and concluded with presenting specific examples of QKD networks implementations.

Section 2: Emerging QKD network technologies focused on analyzing the key supporting technologies of HellasQCI and presented the approaches for Coexistence with optical telecom networks, outlined the Dynamic/switched QKD networks, discussed advanced QKD network controls and concluded by presenting the architecture of the HellasQCI QKD network.

Section 3: Towards the Quantum Internet provided an introduction to the Quantum entanglement and Quantum entanglement distribution networks that are the basic components for the quantum internet and expanded the discussion to Quantum teleportation and Quantum repeaters. Section 3 concluded with the steps that are planned for the HellasQCI quantum entanglement distribution network.

- **“QKD with PQC for a Healthcare use case”** by Homer Papadopoulos

The presentation focused on advancing cybersecurity in the quantum computing era by moving from traditional "safe" encryption to "Quantum safe" methods. It emphasized that QKD devices alone are insufficient for healthcare scenarios due to practical limitations. The presentation included Post-Quantum Cryptography (PQC) and Homomorphic Encryption as quantum-resistant techniques. The HellasQCI Healthcare use case demonstrated the integration of QKD, PQC, and Homomorphic Encryption, creating a hybridized approach to enhance the protection of sensitive healthcare data against emerging cyber threats in the quantum era.

- **“From billion photons to single photon experimental setups”** by Giannis Giannoulis

This section introduces the principles behind the operation of single-photon blocks included in the quantum layer implementation of QKD system architectures. The short course discusses the main principles and some theoretical topics for implementing photonic blocks in support of the development of polarisation encoded QKD systems and their evaluation through QBER measurements. The purpose of this section is to understand the differences between classical communication and QKD-related setups and the challenges of photonic circuitries and setups in real-world transmission quantum links and QKD network deployments.

- **“Theoretical background and equipment description for hands-on experiments”** by Aris Stathis & Argiris Ntanos

This section delves deeper into the physical appearance of a simple in-house experimental setup. The objective is to gain practical insights into the common components comprising a QKD system. The short course is divided into four parts. Section 1 focuses on the technique enabling classical laser sources to generate single photons. Section 2, covers the principles governing the detection of single photons, discussing the essential characteristics and its associated terminology. Section 3 includes classical and quantum signals coexistence over fiber and free space, providing a hands-on demonstration of such an experiment setup. Finally, a comprehensive description of the experimental setup utilized for hands-on lab training is given. This includes a discussion on the operational principles of each component, along with details on experimental parameters, methodologies, and outcomes.

- **“QKD in Space, satellite-to-ground QKD links”** by Nikos Lyras & Argiris Ntanos

This section serves as an outline of optical satellite communication systems focusing on the QKD in Space. The short course discusses the main principles of optical satellite communication systems focusing on the propagation impairments of the satellite to ground classical optical and quantum links, highlighting the challenges, the mitigation techniques as well as the opportunities for research and development. As a final step a detailed analysis of the link budget of a satellite to ground QKD link is explained, and indicative results are showcased. The purpose of this course is to provide an introduction to the QKD and optical satellite communication systems.

3.1 Hands-on Training of basic principles of QKD at NTUA

The goal of these laboratory activities was the introduction of basic components included in the quantum layer of polarisation-encoded DV-QKD systems as well the implementation of quantum links propagating over wireless FSO links and coexisting with classical data streams in optical fibers. The experimental sessions were installed and were demonstrated at the premises of Photonics Communication Research

Laboratory of School of Electrical and Computer Engineering of National Technical University of Athens (**Figure 2**). More specifically, the generation of weak coherent states by attenuating laser sources, the manipulation of photon states using simple polarization optics, the polarization analysis and the detection through a pair of InGaAs SPADs. Moreover, a short-distance FSO link was installed via a pair of collimators for showcasing the successful exchange of polarization-encoded states over the air. At the end, the demonstration of an optical telescope suitable for satellite-QKD links was also included, focusing on the coupling between the optical beams and the fiber cores.

Figure 2: Photo from the training in Photonics Communications Research Laboratory of NTUA

Generation of Polarization Encoded single photons

In **Figure 3** a single photon exchange setup installed in training event, based on attenuated weak coherent light pulses is illustrated. By using a Continuous Wavelength (CW) laser source emitting at 1550.12 nm, pulses were generated through 10 MHz modulation via a Mach-Zehnder Modulator and attenuated with the use of a Variable Optical Attenuator (VOA) to achieve a mean photon number per pulse of $\mu=0.5$. The attenuation stage down to single-photon level was implemented by using a combination of power splitters and variable optical couplers. Optical power monitors were used to calculate the mean photon number of pulse-train. In the presented setup Alice solely prepared vertically polarized photons by using a Polarization Beam Splitter (PBS) in the emission stage. The goal of this demo-experiment was to demonstrate the encoding of single-photon states as well the intensity modulation stage required for controlling the mean photon number of signal/decoy states in QKD protocols.

Figure 3: Single-photon exchange setup based on Weak Coherent Light (Alice side)

Polarization Analysis and Detection setup

The polarisation analysis at the quantum receiver station depicted at **Figure 4** **Error! Reference source not found.** was demonstrated via the use of a polarisation beam splitter (PBS) providing the analysis on the H/V basis. For the compensation of the polarization drift due to the fiber transmission Polarization Controller (PC) was used, therefore the quantum signal was exclusively directed to one of the two InGaAs Single Photon Avalanche Diodes (SPADs). The detection counts were recorded through the graphical user interface of the pair of SPADs, providing the opportunity to showcase the key parameters of the system detection. The dark count rates of both InGaAs SPADs were recorded in both free-running and gated mode, detection efficiencies of both 10% and 20% were demonstrated, and the essential parameter of dead time was calibrated allowing for different detection efficiencies.

Figure 4: Receiver's side (Bob) of the single photon exchange setup containing the SPADs, PBS, and Polarization Controllers.

Coexistence setup multiplexing classical and QKD signals

To evaluate the performance of QKD signals propagating over telecom fibres carrying classical telecommunication signals, a WDM coexistence setup illustrated in **Error! Reference source not found.** was installed based on the use of WDM multiplexers and tunable optical bandpass filters. By controlling the power level of classical signals, the noise count rates associated with the generation of Spontaneous Raman Scattering (SpRS) noise photons can be controlled. In this way, the degradation of QBER

performance for the polarisation-encoded single-photon exchange links can be measured¹. Different filtering stages based on tuneable bandwidth optical filters were used to highlight the impact of filtering nodes to suppress the presence of SpRS noise count rates in the received detection rates.

Figure 5: WDM Setup for coexisting classical/quantum signals.

FSO-QKD setup using collimators

For the realization of the FSO connection two small-sized air-spaced doublet collimators with a numerical aperture of 24 mm were employed, dedicated for operation within the C-band. The FSO link was set up in laboratory as depicted in **Figure 6**, which ensured the protection of the transmission from the outdoor environment. The goal of this experiment was to demonstrate that polarisation-encoded qubits can be successfully transmitted over the air. Stable raw click rates were successfully detected through the pair of SPADs devoted for the quantum receiver circuit, revealing the stability of the single-photon wireless exchange setup which can be used for demonstrating QKD links in short-reach, metropolitan-scale network links.

¹ A. Ntanos, et al., "Deployment-Oriented Classical/Quantum coexistence in X-haul fiber link for B5G Networks," in *CLEO 2023, Technical Digest Series* (Optica Publishing Group, 2023), paper AM3N.5.

Figure 6: 1.5m FSO link established in PCRL to demonstrate single photon exchange over free space

Mini Optical telescope for QKD space-segment

The last laboratory session focused on the demonstration of an optical telescope capable to support mini optical ground stations for satellite-QKD networks. In support of this concept, a Schmidt-Cassegrain optical telescope of 280mm aperture used for astronomical observation from NOAA was showed in the laboratory **Figure 7** **Error! Reference source not found.** (left). The key components for making this optical system suitable for earth-to-satellite QKD links were discussed in this session, while emphasis was given on the telescope-to-fiber coupling mechanism. The optical bench for coupling light from the telescope to single-mode fiber was based on an existing design provided by ESA **Figure 7** (right), and it was also briefly discussed as part of the mini-OGS demonstration.

Figure 7: Computerized Commercial telescope with a 28 cm aperture and the prototype of the receiver assembly to couple light into fiber from the telescope.

3.2 Hands-on Training with real QKD equipment at NKUA

The training focused on introducing commercial Quantum Key Distribution (QKD) systems, simulating real-life configurations. The commercial system employed for the training was a Toshiba QKD4.2-MU/MB pair that implements the Toshiba T12 protocol (efficient BB84 protocol with decoy states and phase encoding). Particularly, the demonstration included a QKD optical link over 50 km long fiber, highlighting the impact of this link on the overall system. Additionally, a gradual introduction of two optical channels was demonstrated. These channels co-propagated along with the quantum channel over a 14-kilometer fiber

link, to show the impact of coexistence on the performance of the QKD pair in terms of Secure Key Rate (SKR) and Quantum Bit Error Rate (QBER).

- QKD over 50 km long fiber

The initial experiment involved a 50 km QKD link, as depicted in **Figure 8**. The quantum channel (1310 nm) of the quantum transmitter (Alice) is multiplexed with two service channels at 1529 nm and 1530 nm. The multiplexed signal, initially passing through a 1:2 coupler at the transmitter (Alice), is then transmitted through a 50 km fiber spool, undergoing a 10 dB attenuation. Additionally, a 5 dB attenuator is applied at Alice's transmitter. The 2:1 splitter is employed to deploy an Optical Spectrum Analyzer (OSA) for monitoring the QKD service signal and the classical laser signal that will be used for the next experiments. Following the demonstration of the QKD communication over 50 km, we replaced the 50 km fiber link with a 10m fiber link, comparing the performance of the QKD systems in the two different configurations. The trainees had the opportunity to witness the SKR and QBER changes while the system was operating in different setups. The goal of this demonstration was to show the achievable distance of a commercial QKD system and how attenuation impacts the performance of such a system.

Figure 8: The QKD setup over the 50 km fiber link presented as a diagram

When the fiber link was 10 m, the Secret Key Rate (SKR) increased due to the lower attenuation (a total loss of 11 dB) it encountered. This contrasts with the implementation with the 50 km fiber link, where an additional 10 dB attenuation led to a total loss of 21 dB. Similarly, the Quantum Bit Error Rate (QBER) decreased when transitioning from one setup to the other, as illustrated in **Figure 9** below. In the 50 km setup, the QBER is 3.32% with an SKR of 19 kbps.

Figure 9: SKR and QBER results for the 50 km topology.

- Quantum and classical optical channels coexistence
 In the second experiment of the training, the same QKD pair was utilized, with the quantum channel propagating over a 14 km fiber link instead of the 50 km. In this demonstration we gradually introduced two classical channels in the 14 km link through the 2:1 coupler, as shown in **Figure 10**. Initially, we applied the QKD setup without activating the two classical optical channels. With this approach we characterized the link and calculated attenuation introduced by the optical components, which was approximately 13.8 dB. For the integration of the classical channels, we connected a 4:1 coupler on the second line of the 2:1 coupler where Alice is linked.

Figure 10: The QKD setup over the 14 km fiber link with two classical channels introduced, presented as a diagram

The first laser (Laser 1), that was introduced, operated at 1550 nm with power level of -2 dBm. More specifically, it was modulated with Non-Return-to-Zero (NRZ) modulation by using a Mach-Zehnder interferometer. This modulation was designed to emulate a real life modulated optical channel at a frequency of 10 GHz. After some minutes, when the QKD system had stabilized, we inserted the second laser (Laser 2). This laser operated at 1549 nm with a power level of -2.5 dBm and functioned as a continuous wave laser (CW).

We investigated the impact of coexistence by gradually activating the lasers. Upon activating the first laser, we observed a degradation in QKD performance, affecting both Secret Key Rate (SKR) and Quantum Bit Error Rate (QBER). This observation is supported by an increase in noise levels measured in the range of 1276 nm to 1326 nm, as detected with the OSA. The broad spectrum of the lasers, generating photons also in the 1310 nm channel, contributed to this outcome, impacting negatively on the QKD performance. The same behavior occurred upon activating the second laser which resulted in further degradation in terms of SKR and QBER. The goal for this experiment was to witness how the coexistence of classical optical channels introduced interference and disturbances, leading to an overall increase in total noise leading to decreased SKR. This is a common scenario, which is commonly encountered in experiments investigating the integration of QKD in optical networks.

Figure 11: Photo from the training in the Photonics lab of NKUA

All the above scenarios were shown in the hands-on experience of the HellasQCI workshop. **Figure 11** shows a photo of the Photonics Lab from NKUA during the training.

4. Workshop on Cybersecurity Experts

The 2nd HellasQCI workshop aimed to raise the awareness of the technical community with respect to QKD and related technologies. The two-day event took place in Athens, on 21-23 September 2023. It was jointly organized and delivered by FORTH and NCSR-D. The workshop provided training to security and IT experts managing cryptosystems. These cryptosystems are usually integrated at different layers of a system or a network to provide security services and assurances. The workshop provided the participants with the required background to understand the capabilities of QKD and its potential. Finally, a roadmap for QKD's integration into the existing cybersecurity infrastructures was presented.

The schedule of the workshop is listed in the following tables.

Table 3: 1st Day - September 21st, 2023

09:00 - 09:15	Welcome Session
09:15 – 10:15	<p>Harry Manifavas, FORTH</p> <p>Cybersecurity and the role of Cryptography</p> <p>The Weakest Link Property</p> <p>The Adversarial Setting</p> <p>Cryptography Pitfalls</p> <p>Security and Other Design Criteria</p> <p>Security Strength levels</p>
10:15 - 11:00	<p>Harry Manifavas, FORTH</p> <p>Basic Cryptographic Primitives</p> <p>Symmetric Cryptography</p> <p>Public Key Cryptography</p> <p>Cryptographic Hash Functions</p> <p>Applications of Cryptography in Real Life</p>
11:00 – 11:15	Coffee Break
11:15 – 12:00	<p>Harry Manifavas, FORTH</p> <p>Cryptographic Attacks and Failures</p> <p>Ciphertext-Only and Known-Plaintext Attacks</p> <p>Brute Force Attack</p> <p>Cryptographic Key Length Recommendations</p>

	<p>Public Key Algorithms Security The Factoring Problem</p> <p>Man-in-The-Middle and Replay Attacks Cryptographic Failures: Case Studies</p>
12:00 - 13:00	<p>Emmanouil Papadogiannakis, FORTH</p> <p>Demonstrations</p> <p>Cryptography Demo</p> <p>Attack scenarios Demo</p>
13:00- 14:00	Lunch Break
14:00 – 17:00	<p>Emmanouil Papadogiannakis, FORTH</p> <p>Practice session: Labs and Exercises</p> <p>Exploiting Cryptographic Failures</p> <p>Cipher Misuse</p> <p>Crypto Misconfiguration</p>

Table 4: 2nd Day - September 22nd, 2023

09:00 – 10:00	<p>Harry Manifavas, FORTH</p> <p>Introduction to Post-Quantum Cryptography</p> <p>Quantum Computing Threat Landscape Challenges: Retrospective Decryption</p> <p>Shor’s and Grover’s Algorithms Quantum Computing Threat Mitigation Post-Quantum Cryptography NIST PQC Standardization Effort PQC Transition Recommendations and Cryptographic Agility</p>
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10:00 – 11:00	<p style="text-align: center;">Harry Manifavas, FORTH</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Introduction to QKD</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Quantum Cryptography and Quantum Encryption QKD Use Cases QKD Requirements, Security and Protocols Attacks and Limitations</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Challenges and Criticism Quantum Random Number Generators</p>
11:00 - 11:15	<p style="text-align: center;">Coffee Break</p>
11:15 – 12:00	<p style="text-align: center;">Homer Papadopoulos, NCSR D</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Integrating QKD into the existing Cryptographic Landscape</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Addressing Challenges in Practical Deployments of QKD and Quantum-Safe Cryptography, and Exploring Current Trends</p> <p style="text-align: center;">QKD standardization efforts and challenges</p> <p style="text-align: center;">EuroQCI</p>
12:00 - 13:00	<p style="text-align: center;">Antonis Korakis, George Balaskas, Homer Papadopoulos NCSR D</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Demonstrations</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Extract keys from a QKD device</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Digital signatures with PQC algorithms</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Encrypt files with PQC algorithms</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Enable computations on encrypted data without decryption</p>
13:00- 14:00	<p style="text-align: center;">Lunch Break</p>

14:00 – 17:00	<p>Antonis Korakis, George Balaskas, Homer Papadopoulos NCSR</p> <p>Practice session: labs and exercises</p> <p>Walk through step-by-step instructions for setting up the encryptor and key retrieval from the QKD device. Encrypt your files with AES 256.</p> <p>Set up your own digital signatures using PQC Dilithium library to authenticate yourself to the encryptor.</p> <p>Encrypt your files with PQC Kyber's encryption methods to access the encryptor.</p> <p>Learn the Homomorphic techniques for encrypting your files, enabling secure cloud computations, while maintaining complete data encryption.</p>
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The training program initially covered the principles of cryptography, including asymmetric (e.g., the RSA algorithm) and symmetric (e.g., the AES and OTP algorithms) cryptosystems. Emphasis was given to their security against both classical and quantum computers. An essential part of this program focused on the fundamental principles underlying the basic QKD protocols, providing an overview of their implementation, the threat model, and the path that the QKD promises to deliver quantum safe encryption. Aside from the system overview and implementation of QKD, emphasis was placed on the integration of QKD solutions into the existing cryptographic infrastructure.

The event included a long session focusing on demos, hands-on training, and exercises. In this edition of the training, the practical component was related to practical uses of cryptography as well as the demonstration of attacks which exploit cryptographic failures. Future editions of the practical component will include demonstrations and hands-on training related to the incorporation of QKD into existing secure infrastructures. Since QKD supports symmetric-key algorithms, it cannot replicate all the services offered by public-key cryptosystems. It is expected that it will be combined with Post Quantum Cryptography (PQC) to jointly form the infrastructure of quantum-safe solutions. Therefore, emphasis was also put on PQC and the transition recommendations, from classical algorithms to PQC algorithms, to a combination of PQC and QKD.

Overall, the workshop aimed to bring together actual specifications and constraints of real-world security infrastructures with QKD solutions while discussing scientific and technological challenges related to this integration in practical deployments. At the end of the workshop the trainees were able to understand the basic concepts that underlie its operation.

The content of the **Lectures** is provided in the following list:

In day 1, the event was divided in two sessions:

Introduction to cryptography (4 hours)

- This session provides an introduction to cryptography and the main types of primitives utilized in security mechanisms and security protocols embedded in widely used applications (web, messaging, data storage, data communications, etc.). It briefly covers secret-key cryptosystems (e.g., AES, OTP), public-key cryptosystems (e.g., RSA) and hashing. The introductory course discusses the main principles for the correct application of cryptographic techniques and elaborates on generic and specific attacks taking advantage of cryptographic failures. The purpose of this section is to elaborate on the strengths and weaknesses of these cryptographic primitives considering the realization of quantum computers.

Hands-on session on cryptographic failures (4 hours)

- This section provides a hands-on introduction to how cryptographic failures, such as cipher misuse, misconfiguration, or poor implementation, as well as security protocol manipulation can be exploited to overcome the security defenses of various systems. Additionally, real-world case studies of cryptographic failures are discussed and demonstrated to provide a further insight into the threat landscape and the practical challenges of building cryptographically secure systems.

Figure 12: Photo from the hands-on Cybersecurity Lab

In day 2, the event was divided in two sessions:

Introduction to PQC and QKD (2 hours)

- This section introduces the quantum computing threat landscape in relation to cybersecurity and the currently available cryptography-based protection mechanisms. It provides an overview of the threats quantum computers pose to established symmetric and asymmetric crypto systems. It discusses the alternatives for mitigating the new risks. More specifically, it elaborates on Post Quantum Cryptography and Quantum Key Distribution as well as related matters, like cryptographic agility, standardization efforts and transition recommendations. Finally, it briefly presents the limitations and challenges these two new technologies are currently facing.

Integrating efforts of Quantum Key Distribution and Quantum-Safe Cryptography in real life use cases (2 hours)

- The presentation provided comprehensive insights into the integration of QKD within the existing cryptographic landscape, the ongoing efforts and challenges in QKD standardization, and the EuroQCI initiative. It highlighted the practical challenges in deploying QKD, such as infrastructure compatibility, cost implications, and scalability. Also discussed were the technical hurdles like distance limitations and the need for reliable quantum repeaters. I also explored the latest trends in quantum-safe cryptography, emphasizing the need for a hybrid approach that combines traditional and quantum-resistant algorithms to ensure long-term data security. The presentation highlighted the progress in standardizing QKD protocols and technologies and presented an overview of the EuroQCI initiative, an important step by the European Union towards establishing a quantum communication infrastructure across Europe.

Demonstrations in PQC and QKD systems and networks (1 hours)

- This session focused on the training in Quantum Communication Infrastructure (QCI) and Quantum Key Distribution (QKD) systems and networks. It included discussions on PQC/QKD use cases, particularly for organizations exchanging sensitive data like hospitals, governmental facilities, military, financial institutions, and research institutes. The session also covered the architecture of these systems, including server rooms, SSL, PQC Encryption, Digital Signature, and the use of AES/QKD for secure data exchange. Additionally, it detailed the software and hardware specifications, including operating systems, programming languages, and device characteristics, and explained the process of encryption and decryption using QKD encryptors.

Practice session: labs and exercises for setting up a QKD network (2 hours)

- This session focused on practical exercises involving quantum key distribution (QKD) encryptors. Key topics included downloading and installing necessary software, generating PQC digital signature keys, uploading public keys to the encryptor, and using the End User Application for encryption and decryption processes. This hands-on approach aimed to familiarize participants with the operational aspects of QKD encryptors in secure communication networks.

Homomorphic Encryption Lab (1 hour)

- This interactive session focused on practical exercises in homomorphic encryption using Python and related libraries. It began with the installation of prerequisite Python packages and an introduction to homomorphic encryption. The lab covered the strengths and limitations of the Microsoft SEAL implementations and the TenSEAL Python library. Participants engaged in encrypting and decrypting data, understanding supported operations like addition, subtraction, multiplication, and matrix operations. The session also included a use case demonstration involving a secure cloud application for medical image classification, showcasing client and server-side operations. The lab was designed to provide hands-on experience with homomorphic encryption techniques and their applications in secure data processing.

The lectures covered the following material:

- The context of Cryptography (1h)
 - The Role of Cryptography
 - The Weakest Link Property
 - The Adversarial Setting
 - Threat Model
 - Cryptography is Not the Solution
 - Cryptography is Difficult
 - Security and Other Design Criteria
 - Security Level
- Cryptographic Primitives (1h)
 - Symmetric Cryptography
 - Modes of Operation
 - Algorithms
 - Shortcomings
 - Public Key Cryptography
 - Confidentiality and Authentication
 - Distribution of Public Keys
 - Hybrid Encryption
 - Digital Signatures
 - Algorithms
 - Cryptographic Hash Functions
 - Properties and Collision Resistance
 - Applications
 - Algorithms
- Cryptographic Attacks & Failures (1h)
 - Cryptographic Attacks
 - Ciphertext-Only Attack
 - Known-Plaintext Attack
 - Brute Force
 - Cryptographic Key Length Recommendations
 - Public Key Algorithms Security
 - The Factoring Problem

- Man-in-The-Middle Attack
- Replay Attack
- Cryptographic Failures
 - Case Studies
- Introduction to Post-Quantum Cryptography (1h)
 - Quantum Computing
 - Applications to Cybersecurity
 - Quantum Advantage/Supremacy
 - Quantum Computing Threat Landscape
 - Public-key and Symmetric-key Cryptography
 - Retrospective Decryption
 - Shor's Algorithm
 - Grover's Algorithm
 - Quantum Computing Threat Mitigation
 - Post-quantum Cryptography
 - NIST PQC Standardization Effort
 - PQC Transition Recommendations
 - Cryptographic Agility
- Introduction to QKD (1h)
 - Quantum Cryptography
 - Quantum Key Distribution
 - Use Cases
 - Quantum Encryption
 - QKD Requirements
 - QKD Security
 - QKD Protocols: BB84
 - Attacks
 - Limitations
 - Challenges and Criticism
 - Quantum Random Number Generators
- Demonstration in PQC and QKD systems and networks (1 hour)
 - PQC/QKD use cases
 - Architecture
 - User wants to encrypt data
 - User wants to decrypt data
 - Encryptor/decryptor characteristics
 - Encryptor/decryptor usage
 - Encryptor communication with QKD
 - QKD Encryptors
 - End User App characteristics

The lecture slides were shared with the participants and include several references for further reading.

Hands-on training

We always assume that there is an adversary trying to exploit vulnerabilities in systems. It is important to understand what we are trying to protect in order to utilize the proper mechanisms and procedures. Cryptography is a vital part of security defenses, but it is complex and prone to implementation or configuration mistakes. Several entities classify these mistakes into categories to inform and direct the

practitioners in their effort to fix system vulnerabilities. The hands-on session was motivated by real-world cases and focused on specific examples. Sample attack and defend protocols were presented for educational purposes. The following two figures (**Figure 13** and **Figure 14**) summarize the demos and the exercises that were run during the lab session.

Figure 13: High level details of the cryptography demo and lab sessions

1. **Demo: Attacking a social network**
 1. Eavesdropping (un)encrypted traffic
 2. Password cracking: Brute forcing hashed passwords
 3. Password cracking: Dictionary and social engineering
2. **Demo: Bypassing authentication**
 1. JWT introduction
 2. Attacking JWT
 3. Demonstrating the ROCA vulnerability
3. **Encryption Modes**
 1. Padding attack
 2. ECB v. CBC
 3. ECB encrypted passwords attack
4. **OTP Key Reuse**
 1. Perfect security
 2. OTP reuse
 3. Many-time pad
5. **Man-In-The-Middle**
 1. Modifying ECB traffic
 2. Rogue CA authority
6. **Poor Random Number Generator**
7. **Benchmarking**
 1. AES v. RSA
 2. DES brute forcing
1. **Storing cryptographic keys**
 1. Stealing hardcoded keys via reverse engineering
 2. Stealing passwords from browser databases
2. **Shamir Secret Sharing**

Figure 14: Low level details of the cryptography demo and lab sessions

The hands-on session for QKD network and Homomorphic encryption was motivated by real-world cases (setting up a QKD network between Hospitals and utilizing Homomorphic encryption to secure cloud-based healthcare services) and focused on the following demos and exercises that were run during the two lab sessions.

Figure 15: Photo from the hands-on Lab for QKD and PQC demonstration

- Practice session: labs and exercises for setting up a QKD network (2 hours)
 - Download-install the required software
 - Generate PQC Digital Signature Keys
 - Upload your public key to the Encryptor
 - Start the end user application
 - Import your digital signature keys to the End User App
 - Encrypt-decrypt using PQC
 - Encrypt-decrypt using the email / USB stick / other messaging application

Figure 16: Applications used by trainees for setting up the QKD network (User Interface for Key Generation Application)

- Homomorphic Encryption Lab (1 hour)
 - Installation of Prerequisite Python Packages
 - Introduction to Homomorphic Encryption
 - Import the Datasets
 - Strengths and Limitations of Microsoft SEAL and TenSEAL

- Encrypt and Decryption techniques
- Supported Operations (Addition, Subtraction, Multiplication, etc.)
- Inside view of the client-side of a secure cloud application for medical image classification
- Use case Aim and Implementation
- Client-Side View
- Server-Side View
- Additional Resources

The screenshot shows a Jupyter Notebook interface with a dark theme. The title is "Homomorphic Encryption Lab By NCSR Demokritos" and the authors are listed as "George Balaskas, Antonis Korakis, Homer Papadopoulos". The notebook content includes a welcome message, an agenda with five items, and a section for installing prerequisite Python packages. A code cell at the bottom contains the following commands:

```
[ ] | git clone https://gitlab.com/ncsr/homomorphic-encryption-lab.git
    | cd /content/homomorphic-encryption-lab
    | !ls
```

Figure 17: Homomorphic Encryption Lab Notebook used for the training

5. HellasQCI training platform

Moodle, an acronym for Modular Object-Oriented Dynamic Learning Environment, represents a prominent open-source Learning Management System (LMS) that has garnered widespread adoption in educational institutions globally. Developed by Martin Dougiamas, the system's inception in 2002 was driven by a commitment to fostering dynamic and interactive online learning environments. Embodying the principles of constructivism and social constructivism, Moodle serves as a versatile platform facilitating the creation, management, and delivery of educational content, thereby engendering collaborative learning experiences. At its core, Moodle is characterized by its modular architecture, enabling the integration of diverse plugins and extensions that extend its functionality. The system supports various instructional formats, such as forums, quizzes, assignments, and multimedia content, providing educators with a comprehensive toolkit to design engaging courses. Noteworthy is Moodle's emphasis on inclusivity and accessibility, as it endeavors to accommodate diverse learning styles and user needs through customizable themes and adaptable content presentation.

Authentication mechanisms within Moodle exhibit flexibility, encompassing options like LDAP integration, manual enrollment, and email-based registration. User roles, including administrators, teachers, and students, are meticulously configured to delineate distinct responsibilities and permissions. This nuanced user management system contributes to the establishment of a structured and secure educational environment. Furthermore, Moodle embodies a robust grading and assessment framework, featuring diverse evaluation tools such as quizzes with configurable parameters, assignments with customizable grading rubrics, and forums for collaborative discourse. The platform's communication and collaboration features, including messaging systems and discussion forums, foster interactive learning communities, promoting dialogue and knowledge exchange among participants.

In essence, Moodle transcends the conventional boundaries of traditional education, offering a scalable and adaptable framework for institutions seeking to leverage technology in the service of pedagogical objectives. Its open-source nature, coupled with a vibrant community of developers and educators, ensures continuous evolution, making Moodle an enduring and transformative force in the realm of online education.

Moodle version 4.2 was used to create HellasQCI material platform. The server is located at Demokritos premises and has the specs following:

- CPU AMD Ryzen 9 5950X AM4/3,4 GHz/72 MB
- Motherboard Gigabyte X570S AERO G
- RAM Desktop Corsair 64 GB Kit 3200 MHz
- SSD Samsung 980 Pro NVMe M.2 1TB
- Corsair CPU Hydro Cooler H150i RGB White
- PSU Corsair HX Series 1200 W80+ Platinum
- Case Corsair Obsidian 7000D Airflow TG

The specific platform is available in any operating system and browser it is running on mysql.

Authentication and User Management

In Hellas QCI training platform for authentication method, it uses the email-based self-registration with admin confirmation. Email-based self-registration with admin confirmation is a user registration method that allows individuals to create their own accounts on the platform using their email addresses. However,

instead of gaining immediate access to the system, the registration requires approval from an administrator before the user can log in. This is a common approach to ensure that only authorized users are granted access to the Moodle site. The steps to create a new user are as follows:

First, go to the training page <https://training.hellasqci.eu/>, then select the log in option at the top right.

Figure 18: Online training platform Main Page

Then choose the “Create new account” button.

Figure 19: Online training platform User Registration page

Here the user enters his/her personal information.

Figure 20: Online training platform new account Information page

Then the user sees the following message saying that it is waiting for approval from the page administrator.

Figure 21: Online training platform User Registration Confirmation message

When the administrator of the page approves the preparation, the following message will be sent to the email that was filled in the form. By clicking on the link in the mail and the registration is complete, the user now has access to the platform.

Figure 22: Online training platform User Registration completion

Every user has a separate role. The roles are determined by the type of the user. The three roles are: administrator, teacher, student. The administrator is responsible for configuring the page, the teacher is responsible for promoting the material on the platform and the students for the operation of the page.

As soon as the users receive access to the training platform can navigate to the home page and access the course they have already been enrolled.

Figure 23: Online training platform Course page

Course Management

The course material has been taken from the HellasQCI 1st training event and the organization of the educational material was based on the pedagogical goals that have been set taking into account the following objectives:

1. Introduction to quantum computer science
2. Introduction to quantum cryptography
3. Understanding practical application of quantum computing

Content Management

The courses consist of a series of video lectures from the HellasQCI 1st training event as well as the presentations shown during these lectures. To display the video on the platform, Moodle's default application was used to play the video as we see in the example below from the course settings.

Figure 24: Online training platform Course settings page

For the integration of the presentations on the platform, a third-party application was used to ensure the safety of the slides from any cases of downloading without the consent of their creators. The application used is called FlipPDF which converts the slides from pdf or ppt format to flipbook format like the example below.

Figure 25: Online training platform Flipbook presentation example

The visitors of the page can navigate among the topics of the course and choose to view one of the presentations. They can turn the pages of the flipbook while at the same time they watch the video of the presenter.

Figure 26: Online training platform Video & Flipbook presentation

Communication and collaboration

Moodle provides a comprehensive messaging system and notification features to facilitate communication and interaction among users within the platform. Below is an overview of the messaging system and notifications in a default Moodle platform:

A. Messaging system:

- **Instant Messaging:** Moodle includes a real-time messaging system that allows users to send instant messages to each other. Users can see who is online and initiate private conversations.
- **Contact List:** Users have a contact list where they can add and manage contacts, making it easier to communicate with classmates, teachers, and other users.
- **Offline Messages:** If a user is offline, messages are stored, and they receive notifications upon logging in.

B. Notifications:

- **Personal Notifications Preferences:** Each user can customize their notification preferences. They can choose how they want to be notified (email, on-site, or both) for different types of events, such as forum posts, assignment submissions, and upcoming deadlines.

- Site-Wide Announcements: Administrators can send site-wide announcements to all users. These announcements can be displayed prominently on the platform, ensuring that important information reaches all users.
- Course-Specific Notifications: Users can receive notifications specific to the courses they are enrolled in. This includes updates on new content, forum posts, and other course-related activities.
- Email Notifications: Users can opt to receive notifications via email. This is especially useful for users who prefer to stay updated outside the Moodle platform

C. Alerts and reminders:

- Upcoming Events: Moodle provides a calendar feature that users can populate with important dates. Users receive alerts and reminders about upcoming events, assignments, and deadlines.
- Activity Completion Alerts: Users can receive notifications upon completing certain activities or meeting specific criteria within a course.
- Completion Tracking: Users can track their progress within a course, and notifications can be configured to update them on their completion status.

Security measures

Users who have access to the platform are approved by the platform administrator thus ensuring the safety of the platform. In case the administrator detects any suspicious behavior from a user, he can warn him, limit him and even delete him from the platform. The user management page from the administrator is as shown in the following **Figure 27**.

The screenshot shows the Moodle user management interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with 'Home', 'Dashboard', 'My courses', and 'Site administration'. Below this, the course name 'TRAINING HELLASQCI' is displayed. A search bar is present on the right. The 'Users' tab is selected, showing '8 USERS'. A 'NEW FILTER' section allows filtering by 'User full name'. Below the filter is a table with the following columns: First name / Last name, Email address, City/Town, Country, Last access, and Edit. The table contains 8 rows of user data, all from Greece. The 'Edit' column for each row includes icons for edit, delete, and 'Confirm / Resend email'.

First name / Last name	Email address	City/Town	Country	Last access	Edit
			Greece	35 days 20 hours	⊙ ⊙ ⊙
			Greece	Never	⊙ ⊙ ⊙ Confirm / Resend email
			Greece	91 days 21 hours	⊙ ⊙ ⊙
			Greece	98 days 20 hours	⊙ ⊙ ⊙
			Greece	6 secs	⊙ ⊙ ⊙
			Greece	Never	⊙ ⊙ ⊙ Confirm / Resend email
			Greece	34 days 20 hours	⊙ ⊙ ⊙
			Greece	1 day 20 hours	⊙ ⊙ ⊙

Figure 27: Online training platform course users' management page

Customization

For the customization of the page, the ENLIGHTLITE theme was used due to the flexible user interface, as well as the color palette of the theme matches that of the HellasQCI page.

Figure 28: Online training platform customization page

Backups and maintenance

In the event of a problem with the page, all the content of the platform has been saved in the NCSR DEMOKRITOS database so that it is available at any time to be used again on the platform.

Course content

The topics that are included in the course follow the agenda of the 1st training event.

General Information:

Figure 29: General Information Course Section

Plenary session:

Figure 30: Plenary session Course Section

Theory about QKD Networks:

Figure 31: Theory About QKD Networks Course Section

Theory for hands-on experimental valuation of QKD principles:

Figure 32: Theory for Hands-on Experimental Valuation of QKD principles Course Section

Hands-on lab courses for QKD principles:

Figure 33: Hands-on Lab Courses for Qkd Principles Course Section

Practical applications and use cases for QKD:

Figure 34: Practical Applications and Use Cases for QKD Course Section

Introduction to cryptography:

Figure 35: Introduction to cryptography Course Section

Hands-on session on cryptographic failures:

Figure 36: Hands on session on cryptographic failures Course Section

Introduction to PQC and QKD:

Figure 37: Introduction to PQC and QKD Course Section

Theory for hands-on session on PQC and Homomorphic encryption and QKD:

Figure 38: Theory for hands-on session on PQC and Homomorphic encryption and QKD Course Section

As conclusion, the training HellasQCI platform provides the speeches and presentations of the HellasQCI trainings for the purpose of providing information about quantum computing. The platform has been configured in such a way that users can access the event material in an easy-to-use environment.

Training menu in HellasQCI website

Figure 39: Training menu HellasQCI website

An overview of the main functionalities of the pages related to training activities of the project follows.

Join HellasQCI Training Events (<https://hellasqci.eu/join-hellasqci-training-events/>)

In this page it is given an overview of the HellasQCI training events policy.

Figure 40: Training events policy

HellasQCI Training Courses -> First Training Event page information (<https://hellasqci.eu/first-training-event/>)

Figure 41: First training event information page

First Training Event page information page includes the following sections.

Program of the workshop on Quantum Key Distribution Systems

Two-Day Training Event on Cybersecurity with QKD Systems and Post-Quantum Cryptography (PQC)

Subscription Form was also available to visitors:

If you cannot 'view' the subscription form, please remove any third party 'adblocker'

1st Quantum Key Distribution (QKD) workshop for researchers

Registration of participants

 Register in all events
 Register in Workshop on Quantum Key Distribution (QKD) Systems
 Register in Workshop on Cybersecurity with QKD Systems and Post-Quantum Cryptography (PQC)
 Select in case you need to receive a certificate of attendance
 I'm not a robot [Privacy](#) [Terms](#)

Subscribe

Figure 45: Subscription form

Through this form they were subscribed to the email list of the participants, in order to receive all the required information such as the email of guidelines.

The HellasQCI's 4day training event is just around the corner!

Only 3 days left for the four-day training course on Cybersecurity featuring Quantum Key Distribution (QKD) systems and Post-Quantum Cryptography (PQC).

Here are the event details:

- 📅 Date: **September 18–19 and 21–22, 2023**
Registration: 8.30 a.m.
 - 📍 Venue: **Multimedia Amphitheatre on the basement of the NTUA Central Library (NTUA Campus Zografou), Greece.**
 - 📍 Google Maps Directions: <https://goo.gl/maps/Zq8TUMAWMx7Q2qQA>
 - 📄 HellasQCI 4day Training Agenda: <https://hellasqci.eu/first-training-event/>
- This event is organized by #HellasQCI, a project managed by #GRNET. It's a unique opportunity to explore Quantum Cryptography and Post-Quantum Cryptography, featuring expert speakers and valuable insights.
- Event Partners:**

- National Infrastructures for Research and Technology (GRNET S.A.)
- National Technical University of Athens
- Aristotle University Of Thessaloniki
- National and Kapodistrian University of Athens
- FORTH-Institute of Computer Science
- NCSR "DEMOKRITOS"
- Space Hellas

Click [here](#) for directions of how to get to the location of the event

For more information call: Mrs Poly Vlassi, Tel: +306936 779129, email: polyvlassi@mail.ntua.gr

Thank you for your interest in attending this training event and we are looking forward to welcoming you there.

HellasQCI Events Committee

Figure 46: Email invitation to participants

After the event a certificate of attendance was sent to participants who requested this through the subscription form (Figure 47):

Figure 47: Certificate of attendance

After the event, an assessment report and a summary infographic were designed and are posted on the portal's Newsfeed page. The infographic was also posted on social media (Facebook, Twitter and LinkedIn).

Figure 48: Infographic

A satisfaction questionnaire was sent to the participants, which when completed also gave access to the HQCI training portal (**Figure 49**).

If you cannot 'view' the survey form, please remove any third party 'adblocker'

HellasQCI 1st training workshop Post-Questionnaire

We would appreciate if you could take the time to answer the questions of this questionnaire carefully and provide us with any additional comments. This questionnaire focuses on the HellasQCI 1st training workshop held in September 2023.

We expect that it should take you no longer than 5 minutes to complete.

Your feedback is very important to the evaluation of the efforts in WPs and for the success of the training within and beyond the HellasQCI project.

Email *

Name *

Organisation/Company *

Role/Job Title *

The objectives of the HellasQCI training workshop were clearly defined and met *

Figure 49: 1st training event post questionnaire

An email was sent to participants to subscribe to the above list and apply their questionnaire (**Figure 50**).

Figure 50: 1st training event email invitation for the application of the post questionnaire

The monitoring and collection of statistics and analytics related to the project website and the email lists was achieved through the privacy preserving tool, matomo (<https://matomo.org/>). The following data were extracted from participants replies and data statistics about their satisfaction from the training event.

<input type="checkbox"/>	NAME	IMPRESSIONS	CONVERSIONS	CONVERSION %
<input type="checkbox"/>	Satisfaction Survey https://hellasqci.n-pages.com/TV1Fau/satisfaction-survey	42	19	45%

Figure 51: Post questionnaire statistics

6. Training Event Media publications

HellasQCI has released the "HellasQCI 4-Day Training Event: Assessment Report 18-19 & 21-22 September 2023, Athens, Greece" on its website and social media accounts. Following this announcement, a journalist from the website www.tomanifesto.gr compiled information from the HellasQCI website and published a corresponding article. Additionally, journalist Yannis Rizopoulos published another article on the website www.netfax.gr. Both articles are in Greek to ensure a broader reach to the public.

The assessment report can be found in the **Annex 1 – HellasQCI Training Event report**.

ΕΛΛΑΔΑ #ΤΕΧΝΟΛΟΓΙΑ #ΑΣΦΑΛΕΙΑ #ΥΠΟΥΡΓΕΙΟ ΨΗΦΙΑΚΗΣ ΔΙΑΚΥΒΕΡΝΗΣΗΣ

HellasQCI: θεωρητικές και πρακτικές γνώσεις στο σεμινάριο για τις κβαντικές τεχνολογίες

To Manifesto Newsroom
26.9.2023

Το ευρωπαϊκό συγχρηματοδοτούμενο έργο [HellasQCI](#) που υλοποιεί το Εθνικό Δίκτυο Κβαντικών Υποδομών της Ελλάδας και συντονίζει το **Εθνικό Δίκτυο Υποδομών Τεχνολογίας και Έρευνας (ΕΔΥΤΕ Α.Ε. – GRNET)**, φορέας του **Υπουργείου Ψηφιακής Διακυβέρνησης**, πραγματοποίησε το πρώτο εκπαιδευτικό σεμινάριο κατάρτισης στις 18-19 και 21-22 Σεπτεμβρίου 2023, στο **Εθνικό Μετσόβιο Πολυτεχνείο (ΕΜΠ) στην Αθήνα**.

Figure 52: Screenshot from the publication of HellasQCI 1st training event at www.tomanifesto.gr website

<https://tomanifesto.gr/hellasqci-theoritikes-kai-praktikes-gnoseis-sto-seminario-gia-tis-kvantikes-technologies-153848>

Το μέλλον της κυβερνοασφάλειας είναι κβαντικό

Τετραήμερο εκπαιδευτικό σεμινάριο για το έργο HellasQCI

Σε μια εποχή που η καθημερινότητά μας εξαρτάται ολοένα περισσότερο από την ψηφιακή τεχνολογία, η κυβερνοασφάλεια αποτελεί κείμενο παράγοντα, από τον οποίο ουσιαστικά εξαρτάται η ίδια η επιβίωσή μας. Οι κβαντικές τεχνολογίες -ώριμες πια και έτοιμες να ανταποδώσουν στην κοινωνία όσα έχουμε επενδύσει

επάνω τους- θα αρχίσουν τα επόμενα χρόνια να δίνουν λύσεις σ' αυτό και πολλά άλλα θέματα, που ξεκινούν από τη μετεωρολογία και τους ταχύτερους υπολογιστές και φτάνουν ως την Τεχνητή Νοημοσύνη και τη Μηχανική Μάθηση. Όμως, πριν από την εφαρμογή, πρέπει βεβαίως να προηγηθούν η (θεωρητική και πρακτική) εκπαίδευση και εξοικείωση των χρηστών κι αυτός ακριβώς είναι ο στόχος του πρώτου τετραήμερου σεμιναρίου, στο πλαίσιο του ευρωπαϊκού συγχρηματοδοτούμενου έργου HellasQCI, που ξεκίνησε χθες, στις φιλόξενες εγκαταστάσεις του ΕΜΠ. Το σεμινάριο, στο οποίο απύθνητο χαιρετισμό ο νέος ΓΓ Τηλεπικοινωνιών και Ταχυδρομείων, Κωνσταντίνος Καραντζάλας υποσχόμενος τη στήριξη του, απευθύνεται στη νέα γενιά μηχανικών, επαγγελματιών της κυβερνοασφάλειας, αλλά και εκπροσώπους της πανεπιστημιακής κοινότητας, φοιτητές, ερευνητές και καθηγητές που εσπάζουν στους τομείς των οπτικών και κβαντικών τεχνολογιών, με απώτερο σκοπό την προετοιμασία της χώρας για τη λειτουργία της Ευρωπαϊκής Υποδομής Κβαντικών Επικοινωνιών EuroQCI, ειδικά σ' ό,τι αφορά στα κβαντικά «κλειδιά» και τη μετα-κβαντική κρυπτογραφία.

Εταίροι και συνέργειες

Εκτός από τους εταίρους του «HellasQCI» (Εθνικό Δίκτυο Υποδομών Τεχνολογίας και Έρευνας, Εθνικό Μετσόβιο Πολυτεχνείο, Αριστοτέλειο Πανεπιστήμιο Θεσσαλονίκης, Εθνικό & Καποδιστριακό Πανεπιστήμιο Αθηνών, Ίδρυμα Τεχνολογίας και Έρευνας, ΕΚΕΦΕ «Δημόκριτος», Αστεροσκοπείο Αθηνών και Space Hellas, στο σεμινάριο συμμετέχουν επίσης -αναδεικνύοντας τον διεθνή χαρακτήρα της ελληνικής προσπάθειας- απεσταλμένοι από τους διεθνείς εταίρους, τα αντίστοιχα Εθνικά Δίκτυα Κβαντικών Επικοινωνιών της Ιρλανδίας, της Πολωνίας, και της Κύπρου. Στην εναρκτήρια συνεδρίαση του σεμιναρίου και μετά τον χαιρετισμό του προέδρου του ΕΔΥΤΕ, καθ. Στέφανου Κόλλια, η κύρια ομιλήτρια, δρ. Ελένη Διαμαντή (διευθ. ερευνών του CNRS, στη Σαρβάνη), έδωσε τη διεθνή εικόνα των δυνατοτήτων των κβαντικών τεχνολογιών και των εφαρμογών τους με συγκεκριμένα παραδείγματα από τη Χημεία, τη Φαρμακολογία, τις Χρηματοοικονομικές υπηρεσίες, τα νέα Υλικά, την Ιατρική, τη Μετεωρολογία, την Άμυνα, και, φυσικά, την ασφάλεια, ειδικά των κρίσιμων υποδομών, τονίζοντας ότι μπορούμε να καταφέρουμε πολλά. Την ελληνική πραγματικότητα (ενταγμένη, προφανώς, στην ευρωπαϊκή εικόνα, όπου οι προτάσεις μας διακρίνονται ιδιαίτερα - πέρυσι, αναδείχθηκαν δεύτερες καλύτερες στην ΕΕ) περιέγραψε το στέλεχος του ΕΔΥΤΕ και συντονιστής του HellasQCI, Δρ. Ηλίας Παπασαματίου. Ανέλυσε τη δομή του επίγειου (ετοιμάζονται 12 κόμβοι ανά την Ελλάδα) και του δορυφορικού σκέλους (γίνονται εργασίες στα αστεροσκοπεία του Χελμού, του Χολομώντα και του Σκίνακα, για την υποδοχή των κβαντικών σημάτων και τη σύνδεση με τα κοινά μητροπολιτικά κέντρα) και αποκάλυψε πως ο χρονικός στόχος για τη λειτουργία του συστήματος, είναι το 2027.

ΓΙΑΝΝΗΣ ΡΙΖΟΠΟΥΛΟΣ

LANCOM: ΑΝΑΔΕΙΞΗ ΤΗΣ ΧΩΡΑΣ ΣΤΗ ΤΗΛΕΠΙΚΟΙΝΩΝΙΑΚΟ ΚΟΜΒΟ ΤΩΝ ΒΑΛΚΑΝΙΩΝ

Στο Βελγιογράδι και στην Πράγα παρευρέθηκαν για άλλη μία χρονιά τα στελέχη της Lancom συμμετέχοντας στο Central and Eastern Europe Carriers and Enterprises Event και στο European Peering Forum αντίστοιχα. Το CEE CEE Summer Event 2023, που πραγματοποιήθηκε στις 7-8 Σεπτεμβρίου, συγκέντρωσε τα κορυφαία στελέχη του κλάδου των τηλεπικοινωνιών της Κεντροανατολικής Ευρώπης σε στοχευμένες επιχειρηματικές συναντήσεις. Ακολούθως, στις 11- 13 Σεπτεμβρίου στην Πράγα, στο European Peering Forum, μια εκδήλωση έντονου ενδιαφέροντος για τηλεπικοινωνιακού παρόχους και εκπροσώπους Internet Exchanges, τα στελέχη της Lancom πραγματοποίησαν εκτός των τεχνικών σεμιναρίων και πλήθος συνομιλιών με υπάρχοντες και εν δυνάμει συνεργάτες.

Παραγωγικές συναντήσεις

Κατά τη διάρκεια των δύο συνεδρίων, τα στελέχη της Lancom παρουσίασαν το όραμα της εταιρείας για την ανάδειξη της χώρας στο νέο τηλεπικοινωνιακό κόμβο των Βαλκανίων, με όχημα το Balkan Gate Θεσσαλονίκη, το οποίο, όπως αναφέρεται, «πλέον χαιρεί διεθνούς αναγνώρισης καθώς έχει συγκεντρώσει και παρέχει υπηρεσίες φιλοξενίας-διασύνδεσης σε μερικές από τις μεγαλύτερες πολυεθνικές και ελληνικές εταιρείες τηλεπικοινωνιών». «Οι συναντήσεις μας στο εξωτερικό ήταν ιδιαίτερα παραγωγικές, και περιμένουμε να ανακοινώσουμε πολλές νέες σημαντικές συνεργασίες μέσα στους επόμενους μήνες», δήλωσε η διευθύντρια πωλήσεων της Lancom Λένα Ξανθοπούλου.

Figure 53: Screenshot from the publication of HellasQCI 1st training event at NetFAX daily newsletter

7. Conclusions

In summary, this deliverable serves as a comprehensive roadmap outlining the main pillars of the training methodology embedded within the HellasQCI project. It describes a detailed plan to cultivate a robust ecosystem fostering the growth of young researchers, cybersecurity experts, and startups or industrial entities, all working in tandem to strengthen the national QCI. The envisaged national quantum ecosystem is envisioned not only as a hub for expertise, but also as a dynamic entity capable of operating, maintaining, and servicing of the entire HellasQCI infrastructure. The community of HellasQCI is expected also in the future to engage in developing cutting-edge devices and systems related to quantum technologies. This comprehensive approach ensures a forward-looking community compatible with evolving technological demands.

A significant milestone in the execution of the HellasQCI training plan was the successful organization of the first training event under WP5. Two workshops were prepared for the research and academic communities alongside IT security experts and were hosted at NTUA and NKUA facilities during the 3rd week of September 2023. The content of the two workshops were tailored made for the two different target groups and this deliverable offers a description of the workshops' programs with a short presentation of the topics covered by the theory lectures and the hands-on training activities.

Furthermore, the deliverable provides details about the online platform, that was designed as a centralized repository for all training materials generated within HellasQCI so far. This is a critical tool for knowledge dissemination with trainees or other staff related to QKD can effortlessly access and retrieve resources relevant to their respective fields of interest.

Finally, serving as an appendix, the document concludes with a comprehensive report on the first HellasQCI training event. This detailed report encapsulates several information about the event such as attendance metrics, both physical and online attendance facilitated through the GRNET Diavlos livestream service, providing a comprehensive snapshot of engagement and outreach.

8. Annex 1 – HellasQCI Training Event report

HellasQCI 4-Day Training Event: Assessment Report 18-19 & 21-22 September 2023, Athens, Greece

The [HellasQCI project](#) held its first training event on September 18-19 and 21-22, 2023, at the National Technical University of Athens, Greece. The training was designed to provide participants with theoretical and practical knowledge on quantum communication, with the goal of enhancing the security of sensitive data and critical infrastructures in Greece and co-creating EuroQCI.

The 4-day event was launched by the new Secretary General of Telecommunications and Post, Konstantinos Karantzalos, followed by welcoming remarks from Prof. Stefanos Kollias, Chairman of the Board of Directors GRNET S.A. The keynote speech, "Quantum Technologies - QKD Landscape in Europe," was given by Dr. Eleni Diamanti, CNRS research director at Sorbonne University in Paris.

The training was open to cybersecurity professionals, IT managers and engineers, security and IT experts, researchers, students, and practitioners in the field of quantum communication, as well as decision-makers interested in future-proofing their organisation's security infrastructure. Participants could attend in person or via livestream through the [GRNET DIAVLOS](#) service. The event had two different thematic axes, namely the "**Workshop on Quantum Key Distribution (QKD) Systems**" held on 18 and 19 of September and the "**Workshop on Cybersecurity with QKD Systems and Post-Quantum Cryptography (PQC)**" held on 21 and 22 of September. The two workshops were well-received, with an average of 100 attendees at the first workshop and 75 at the second. In total, **175 unique people** attended the workshops. Additionally, an average of **100 people per day participated online** via the GRNET Diavlos livestream service. **Sixteen trainers** provided insights and knowledge on quantum communication.

The new Secretary General of Telecommunications and Post, Konstantinos Karantzalos, addressed a welcome note to commence the 4-Day Training Event. The Secretary General mentioned: “I would like to recognize the previous leadership of the Ministry and GRNET for their work on this important project. I wish everyone a successful start to the 4-day training event”.

The Chairman of the Board of Directors GRNET S.A., Prof. Stefanos Kollias, in his welcome speech stated: “Quantum technology is one of the technologies that already concern us and will be of great interest to us in the coming period. It will have an impact on all sectors. I am personally involved in machine learning and artificial intelligence and we’re trying to develop technologies compatible with quantum technology. So, we found ourselves today at an advanced meeting and training that concerns both engineers, researchers, and students. GRNET, as coordinator of the HellasQCI project, will strive in cooperation with the partner universities to achieve the best education of engineers, students, and researchers in these technologies. I wish you a good start and good luck in this seminar”.

The event was reported on in the NetFax daily digital newsletter (on September 19, 2023), which fully covers Greek and international news in the areas of information technology and telecommunications, the internet, and e-commerce. Journalist Y. Rizopoulos emphasised that *"in an era when our daily lives are increasingly dependent on digital technology, cybersecurity is a critical factor on which our very survival depends."*

With the conclusion of the 4-day event, technical knowledge concerning the implementation of the project and best practices were shared, including information about the:

- Design of the quantum communication architecture, the use-cases and the QKD (quantum key distribution) technologies that will be used throughout the implementation phase, as well as the initial steps for the trainings
- National stakeholder engagement through the HellasQCI community
- National QCI projects from Ireland, Luxembourg and Poland and their aim to build networks using QKD technology within the EuroQCI framework

The 4-day training on quantum communication infrastructure generated strong interest from the Greek and the European quantum community. Social media announcements were made to support and document the important work carried out and succeeded in driving more traffic to the training event, as evidenced by the significant increase in social media engagement and website visits during and after the event. The organisers of both events, in the framework of the HellasQCI project were: GRNET, National Technical University of Athens, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, National and Kapodistrian University of Athens, Foundation for Research & Technology – Hellas, National Centre of Scientific Research "Demokritos" and Space Hellas.

Useful information about the HellasQCI project and the project’s objectives:

- Meeting agenda, trainers and partners available here: <https://hellasqci.eu/first-training-event/>
- Video from the presentation of the project: <https://shorturl.at/sCK13>
- Other useful links and info:
- HellasQCI info page on GRNET website: <https://grnet.gr/en/business-directory/hellasqci-en/>
- [EuroQCI](#) info website page

- HellasQCI Social Media Channels: [Facebook](#), [Twitter](#), [LinkedIn](#), [YouTube](#)

4-Day Training Photo materials

Figure 54: Plenary Session at the Multimedia Amphitheater, NTUA, Athens

Figure 55: Prof. Konstantinos Karantzalos, Secretary General of Telecommunications & Posts, Hellenic Ministry of Digital Governance

Figure 56: Prof. Stefanos Kollias, Chairman of the Board of Directors GRNET S.A.

Figure 57: Keynote speech by Dr. Eleni Diamanti, CNRS research director at Sorbonne University, Paris

Figure 58: Prof. Konstantinos Vyrsokinos (AUTH), Prof. Stefanos Kollias (Chairman of the Board of Directors GRNET S.A.), Prof. Konstantinos Karantzas (Secretary General of Telecommunications & Posts, Hellenic Ministry of Digital Governance), Dr. Ilias Papastamatiou, HellasQCI Project Coordinator, GRNET S.A., Ass. Prof. Kanellos (NKUA - HellasQCI Technical Coordinator), Yannis Rizopoulos, Journalist, Bousias Media

Figure 59: Dr. Homer Papadopoulos, (National Center for Scientific Research Demokritos), Dr. Johanna Sepúlveda Chief Engineer Quantum-Secure Communications, Airbus Defence and Space, Artemis Psarianou BA, DipM, ACIM, MA, AC, (Head of Marketing and Communications Department - GRNET S.A.), Prof. Konstantinos Vyrsokinos (AUTH), Dr. Ilias Papastamatiou, (HellasQCI Project Coordinator, GRNET S.A.), Yannis Rizopoulos, Journalist, (Bousias Media), Dr. Deirdre Kilbane Director of Research in Walton Institute for Information and Communication Systems SETU, IrelandQCI Coordinator, Ass. Prof. Kanellos (NKUA - HellasQCI Technical Coordinator)

Figure 60: Photonics Communications Research Laboratory (PCRL) – Hands-on Experience @ NTUA

Figure 61: Operating Principle of Single Photon Avalanche Detectors (SPAD) - Research Laboratory – Hands-on Experience @ National and Kapodistrian University of Athens